

MORPHOMETRIC FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF ORGANS OF THE BONES OF THE DENTITION IN CHILDREN WITH CHRONIC PATHOLOGIES OF THE RESPIRATORY SYSTEM

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Abstract – In recent years, a significant amount of work has appeared on the study of the relationship between the size of the head and somatotypes and proportions of the human body. [7, 15, 25, 20, 18, 11]. However, as the author [9] points out, anthropometric studies of recent years have shown that the physical status of modern man has undergone certain changes compared to that presented in the works of the mid-20th century and one of the main reasons is that the works devoted to physical development, more attention is paid to the somatotype and much less to the head.

Key words: anthropometric studies, orthodontist, dentoalveolar anomalies, neuro-humoral mechanisms, maturation of organs and systems.

I. Introduction

Everyone knows that the present appearance of a person plays an important role in the formation of personality. The desire to have a beautiful smile, the correct bite is an incentive to contact an orthodontist, in order to correct various types of dentoalveolar anomalies (DAA).

The growth and development of the human body from the stage of the embryo to its adult state is a very complex phenomenon that undergoes many changes under the neuro-humoral mechanisms controlling the differentiation, development and maturation of organs and systems. The growth parameters of various parts of the human body can be influenced by various causes, both physical [4, 5], mental [6], information loads [29], and pathological [12, 26, 13, 35]. According to the author [2], in children and adolescents, female gains in the general growth of the body appear at 7, 12-13 years old, growth gains in the upper part of the face - 11 and 14 years old, lower third - in 11 and 15; the sagittal diameter of the head also increases evenly.

The identification of the morphofunctional community of changes in the dentofacial system (DFS) and the upper respiratory tract (URT) is an important problem in theoretical and practical dentistry, to which many scientists have attracted [17, 16, 1, 12, 13, 26, 10, 27, 30, 36, 22].

II. Literature review

Depending on the duration, oral breathing (OB) can cause numerous functional, structural, postural and behavioral changes, including DFS, which is structurally and functionally closely associated with airway use [19, 28] and in children with nasal breathing difficulties (ID), the risk of developing ASA increased 2-2.5 times [8, 24, 23]. In addition to these factors, there is a close relationship between skeletal growth, fat accumulation, head size, and chronic respiratory system pathologies (ChRSP). Nevertheless, despite this general proportionality, skeletal growth, fat accumulation, and head growth show different models [31]. It was proved that head size and schizophrenia have a close relationship [21], in addition, in children aged 3-6 years, craniofacial sizes showed age-sex ratios independent of body weight and body length [34], another authors found that anthropometric and dental measurements were significantly different in children with obstructive sleep apnea compared with non-snoring [32,33].

An analysis of the literature of domestic and foreign researchers claims that with most diseases, the morphometric parameters of a particular area of the body, including the head and maxillofacial area, change.

The purpose of this study is to determine the morphometric features in children with chronic pathologies of the respiratory system.

III. Analysis

Material and research methods: To study and evaluate the morphometric parameters of the head, face, DFS, bone and tooth age in children with ChRSP, we took 480 children of both sexes aged 6 to 18 years (I group) living in the city of Bukhara; of which 250 boys (52.1%) and 230 girls (47.9%); to compare the obtained morphometric parameters, a group of practically healthy (group II) was taken, the number of 300 children of both sexes aged 6 to 18 years; 185 boys (61.6%) and 115 girls (38.33%); the examined children were distributed by the age category of the examined (table №1).

Table number 1
According to the age group of the children surveyed, n = 780

Age	Boys		Girls		Total
	Healthy children	Children with ChRSP	Healthy children	Children with ChRSP	
6-9	50	75	35	71	231
10-13	65	80	35	79	259
14-18	70	95	45	80	290
Total	185	250	115	230	780

The study of morphometric data on the physical development of all examined children who applied to a specialist and were partially registered in the dispensary of the regional children's and adult multidisciplinary hospitals, and the departments of Orthopedic Dentistry and Orthodontics, Otorhinolaryngology and Pediatrics of the Bukhara State Medical Institute

Anthropometric studies of children were performed according to Shomirzaev N.Kh. [1998]; for morphometric characterization of the head, measurements were performed according to 5 indicators: head girth (HG), longitudinal head diameter (LHD), transverse head size (THS) of vertical or vertical head diameter (VHD), and transverse forehead size (TFS) used a tazomere. To determine the size of the base of the head (skull) was evaluated by the length of the base of the head and the width of the base of the head.

For morphometric evaluation of the parameters, the faces of children were studied (using a special compass and measuring tape): the zygomatic and mandibular diameter (DM and l /j) were also measured with a tazomer; l /j angle (goniometer) with an open mouth; morphological height of the face (MHF); physiognomic height of the face (PhHF) was measured with a tazomer; externally the orbital width and interorbital width were measured with a caliper. In addition, bite conditions were determined with gnathometric methods, but we planned to discuss the results of these data later.

To determine the bone age of the child, the obtained R-we are compared with the standards of bone maturation according to special R-tables; For this, the R-method of the wrist joint and the wrist of the child's left hand was used according to the method of M.A. Jukovsky and others (1982), [3].

The obtained statistical data was processed using a computer (PentiumIV) software package Microsoft Office Excel - 2010, including the use of built-in statistical processing functions. Methods of variational parametric and nonparametric were used, the statistical significance of the measurements when comparing the average quantitative values was determined by the Student criterion (t) with the calculation of the error probability (P). When organizing and conducting research, the principles of evidence-based medicine were used [14].

The primary parameters of physical development include standing standing, body weight and chest circumference in a pause: As can be seen, the results of the study in healthy children showed that the growth in 6-10 year old male children ranged from 114.7 sm up to 134.1 sm, averaging 124.4 ± 0.48 sm. When measured, body weight ranged from 15.8 kg to 31.6 kg, on average it was equal to 24.6 ± 0.33 kg. The chest circumference ranged from 55.4 to 72.9 sm, on average - 62.7 ± 0.38 sm. In 6-10 year old children, the female span ranged from 120.0 sm to 135.4 sm, averaging $128, 8 \pm 0.92$ sm; body weight from 18.1 kg to 35.2 kg, averaging 25.8 ± 0.22 kg; chest circumference ranged from 57.4 to 73.9 sm, on average - 61.0 ± 0.56 sm.

As a result of studies, it was found that the growth in 10-13 year old male children ranged from 134.7 sm to 155.2 sm, averaging 143.9 ± 0.26 sm. Body weight ranged from 17.8 kg to 50, 4 kg, on average it was equal to 37.0 ± 0.98 kg. The chest circumference is in the range from 60.4 to 77.1 sm, on average - 68.2 ± 0.31 sm. For girls 10-13 years old, the growth ranged from 134.4 sm to 159.6 sm, averaging 145.4 ± 0.53 sm; body weight ranged from 25.2 kg to 52.4 kg, on average it was 34.2 ± 0.97 kg; the chest circumference is in the range from 60.6 to 78.5 sm, on average - 69.5 ± 0.36 sm.

Studies have shown that growth in 14-18 year old male children ranged from 148.5 sm to 178.8 sm, averaging 165.1 ± 0.33 sm. Body weight ranged from 49.3 kg to 69.4 kg, on average, was equal to 61.2 ± 0.77 kg. When measuring the chest circumference is in the range from 66.8 to 95.5 sm, on average - 81.0 ± 0.46 sm. The growth in girls aged 14-18 years old ranged from 150.4 sm to 182.4 sm, averaging 166.1 ± 0.23 sm; body weight ranged from 50.3 kg to 71.4 kg, averaging 62.8 ± 0.37 kg; the chest circumference is in the range from 68.8 to 105.5 sm, on average - 93.0 ± 0.26 sm.

The results of the study in patients with ChRSP showed that growth in 6-10 year old male children ranged from 108.5 sm to 133.2 sm, averaging 122.2 ± 0.28 sm. When measured, body weight ranged from 14, 0 kg to 30.6 kg, on average it was equal to 22.6 ± 0.13 kg. The chest circumference was from 50.4 to 70.9 sm, an average of 60.2 ± 0.34 sm. Height in 6-10 year old female children ranged from 111.0 sm to 136.1 sm, an average of $125, 7 \pm 0.72$ sm; body weight ranges from 18.1 kg to 38.1 kg, averaging 24.2 ± 0.42 kg; the chest circumference ranged from 53.3 to 69.9 sm, an average of 57.3 ± 0.47 sm.

As a result, it shows that the growth in 10-13 year old male children ranged from 130.4 sm to 153.2 sm, averaging 141.8 ± 0.16 sm. Body weight ranged from 17.1 kg to 48.4 kg, on average, was 36.0 ± 0.48 kg. The chest circumference ranges from 55.4 to 74.1 sm, an average of 64.5 ± 0.21 sm. At the same age, girls' growth ranged from 131.2 sm to 157.4

sm, averaging 143.5 ± 0.63 sm; body weight ranged from 23.2 kg to 52.8 kg, an average of 33.2 ± 0.47 kg; the chest circumference is in the range from 58.4 to 75.3 sm, on average - 66.9 ± 0.86 sm.

The research results showed that the growth in 14-18 year old male children ranged from 140.5 sm to 170.2 sm, averaging 151.1 ± 0.63 sm. Body weight ranged from 45.4 kg to 65.4 kg, on average it was equal to 58.1 ± 0.98 kg. When measuring the chest circumference is in the range from 64.4 to 90.5 sm, on average - 77.0 ± 0.96 sm. At the same age, the growth of girls' children ranged from 138.4 sm to 178.4 sm, on average amounting to 156.1 ± 0.73 sm; body weight ranged from 47.3 kg to 69.4 kg, averaging 60.1 ± 0.27 kg; when measuring the chest circumference from 64.8 to 100.5 sm, on average 88.9 ± 0.16 sm.

A comparative analysis of the morphometric parameters of the faces of healthy children and children with ChRSP in groups of 6–9, 10–13, and 14–18 years of age showed that the PhHF in 6–9-year-old healthy boys ranged from 16.3 to 18.3 sm, on average 17.1 ± 0.10 sm (growth rate 2.4%), and for girls this parameter varied from 15.9 to 18.4 sm, on average 17.3 ± 0.12 sm (growth rate 4.2%) MHF for boys of this group varied from 10.4 to 12.4 sm, averaging 11.5 ± 0.10 sm (growth rate of 2.7%), and for girls from 10.7 sm to 12.6 sm, an average of 11.2 ± 0.12 sm (growth rate of 2.7%).

PhHF in 6–9-year-old male children has a ChRSP range of 15.3–17.7 sm, an average of 16.6 ± 0.07 sm (growth rate

Physiological height of the face in the examined groups

of 0.6%), and in girls from 16.0 to 17, 5 sm, an average of 17 ± 0.07 sm (growth rate of 2.4%). In 6–9 year old boys who have chronic kidney disease; MHF ranged from 10.0 to 12.0 sm, averaging 11.1 ± 0.10 sm (growth rate of 0.9%), and in girls ranged from 9.4 sm to 12.0 sm, an average of 11.2 ± 0.04 sm (growth rate of 8.6%).

Morphological height of the face in the examined groups

PhHF in 10-13 year old healthy boys ranged from 16.0 to 18.1 sm, an average of 17.2 ± 0.11 sm (no growth rate), and in girls this parameter varied from 17.1 to 19.0 sm , on average 18.2 ± 0.10 sm (growth rate -4.0%). MHF in healthy boys ranged from 10.1 to 12.1 sm, averaging 11.7 ± 0.13 sm (growth rate - 0.9%), and in girls - from 9.9 sm to 12.4 sm , on average 11.8 ± 0.13 sm (growth rate -4.4%).

In 10–13-year-old male children, the ChRSP of PhHF varied from 15.0 to 17.5 sm, an average of 16.5 ± 0.08 sm (growth rate of -0.6%), and in girls from 16.0 to 18, 0 sm, on average 17 ± 0.05 sm (growth rate equal to 1.8%). MHF in 10-13 year old boys of this group ranged from 10.0 to 12.0 sm, averaging 11.0 ± 0.07 sm (growth rate - 1.8%), and in girls ranged from 10, 5 sm to 12.6 sm, an average of 11.5 ± 0.05 sm (growth rate is -0.9%).

Table №2.

Morphometric parameters of a person who is healthier than children and children with ChRSP according to their “principle of the golden ratio”

Age and sex		6-9 age		10-13 age		14-18 age		
		Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	
Param.person (sm)	Physio. face height	Healthy	17,1±0,10	17,3±0,12*	17,2±0,10	17,5±0,12*	18,8±0,40	19,2±0,02*
	ChRSP	16,6±0,07	17±0,05*	16,5±0,08	17,0±0,05*	17,2±0,02	17,4±0,05*	
MHF	Healthy	11,5±0,10	11,2±0,12	11,7±0,13	11,3±0,12	11,9±0,22	11,8±0,01	
	ChRSP	11,1±0,06	11,2±0,04*	11,0±0,07	11,5±0,04*	11,6±0,22	11,6±0,20*	
Height in / part of the face	Healthy	5,8±0,05	5,8±0,05	5,8±0,05	5,8±0,05	5,9±0,08	5,9±0,08	
	ChRSP	5,6±0,03	5,7±0,02	5,7±0,03	5,7±0,02	5,9±0,07	5,9±0,08	
Height of media / parts of the face	Healthy	5,7±0,05	5,9±0,05*	5,8±0,05	5,9±0,05*	5,9±0,08	6,0±0,08*	
	ChRSP	5,5±0,03	5,8±0,02*	5,6±0,03	5,8±0,02*	5,8±0,08	5,9±0,01*	
Height n / a part	Healthy	5,7±0,05	5,9±0,05*	5,8±0,05	5,9±0,05*	6,0±0,05	6,0±0,05*	

of the face	ChRSP	5,7±0,03	5,6±0,02	5,7±0,03	5,6±0,02	5,8±0,08	5,8±0,07
Fibonacci number	Healthy	1:1,611	1:1,60	1:1,619	1:1,60	1:1,680	1:1,70
	ChRSP	1:1,585	1:1,630	1:1,601	1:1,630	1:1,620	1:1,640

Note: * - confidence indicator (P <0.05) compared with the previous age.

Thus, the study showed that MHF and PhHF in children with ChRSP are smaller in size than in healthy children. The growth rate of the morphometric parameters of the face in healthy children is almost the same at regular intervals of time, and in children with ChRSP they change spasmodically. In healthy male children, the growth rate is lower than with male children suffering from ChRSP. It has been established that the ratio of the upper, middle and lower parts of the face in girls of all groups is closer to the "principle of the golden ratio" compared to boys. In children with ChRSP, especially in boys, the ratio of the parts of the face does not correspond to the Fibonacci number.

IV. Discussion

As we said above when determining the child’s bone age, the obtained R was compared with the standards of bone maturation according to special R tables, it was found that in healthy children of males at 6-10 years old, ossification nucleus appeared in the ulnar pineal gland, from 10 years old - in styloid process of the epiphysis of the ulnar bone, and at the age of 14, the ossification core was found in the pisiform bones.

It was established that in children of males suffering from chronic kidney disease at 6 years of age, ossification nuclei are visible only in the capitate and hooked bones of the wrist, and at 10 years of age, ossification nuclei appeared in the ulnar epiphysis, and from the age of 14, into the styloid process of the ulnar epiphysis bones. In children of women with ChRSP, only ossification nuclei are visible in the capitate and hooked bones of the wrist, and ossification nuclei in the trihedral bones of the wrist of the left hand are determined at the beginning of the 6th year of life. At the age of 10 years, the nuclei of ossification in the large and small polygonal bones of the wrist, and at 12 years of age, the nuclei of ossification appeared in the epiphysis of the ulna, at 13 years of age in the styloid process of the epiphysis of the ulna. At the age of 14, there is still no core of ossification in the pea bones.

In healthy children of males, at 6–9 years of age, ossification nuclei are determined in the trihedral bones of the left hand, at 10–13 years, into the styloid process of the ulnar pineal gland, and at an older age, the ossification nucleus is found in the pea bones. The timing of the appearance of ossification nuclei in healthy children of females is the same as in healthy boys.

Morphometric parameters of the head and DFS of children of both sexes of 6-9, 10-13 and 14-18 age groups, healthy children and children ChRSP: he results obtained on the head and DFS of healthy children show that in a 6–9-year-old group of male children, the HG ranged from 48.5 to 60.1 sm, on average - 51.8 ± 0.24 sm, LHD from 13.5 to 16,9 sm, on average - 15.0 ± 0.42 sm, THS varied from 11.5 to 14.0 sm, on average - 12.8 ± 0.56 sm, TFS was from 9.6 to 13.8 sm , on average - 11.4 ± 0.18 sm, VDH ranged from 10.8 to 14.1 cm, on average - 11.8 ± 0.1 cm.

Head and DFS indices in a 6–9 year old group of male children, patients with ChRSP the HG fluctuated from 45.5 to 52.6 sm, on average –48.8 ± 0.22 sm, LDH from 12.5 to 16.9 sm , on average - 14.8 ± 0.14 sm, THS ranged from 11.5 to 14.0 sm, on average - 12.0 ± 0.16 sm, TFS was from 9.4 to 12.8 sm, on average - 11.2 ± 0.06 sm, VHS ranged from 10.2 to 13.1 sm, on average - 12.0 ± 0.04 sm.

The trend of a gradual increase in the size of the head and face continued in the health of male children 10-13 years old, the data showed that the exhaust gas ranged from 50.0 to 58.4 sm, which averaged 54.9 ± 0.14 sm; LDH ranged from 16.8 to 19.6 sm, an average of 17.8 ± 0.03 sm; THS ranged from 12.1 to 18.8 sm, on average it was 15.5 ± 0.19 sm; TFS was in the range of 10.6-16.6 sm, an average of 13.6 ± 0.10 sm and VHS ranged from 12.6 to 16.5 sm, which averaged 15.1 ± 0.10 sm.

Head and DFS indicators of a 10–13-year-old group of male children underwent ChRSP of the exhaust gas ranged from 50.0 to 54.2 sm, which averaged 52.1 ± 0.40 sm; LDH ranged from 15.1 to 18.0 sm, an average of 16.0 ± 0.90 sm; THS ranged from 10.8 to 16.2 sm, the average was 13.2 ± 0.11 sm; TFS was in the range of 10.0-13.5 sm, an average of 11.4 ± 0.28 sm and VHS ranged from 12.0 to 14.0 sm, which averaged 13.0 ± 0.98 sm.

The tendency to increase the size of the head and face continued the trauma of male children 14-18 years old; HG ranged from 51.0 to 60.4 sm, which averaged 55.7 ± 0.14 sm; LDH ranged from 15.8 to 21.6 sm, an average of 18.6 ± 0.13 sm; THS ranged from 12.0 to 19.8 sm, on average it was 16.0 ± 0.10 sm; TFS was in the range of 11.8-17.8 sm, an average of 14.8 ± 0.10 sm and VHS ranged from 12.4 to 18.6 sm, which averaged 16.2 ± 0.10 sm.

The results obtained by morphometric characteristics of the head and DFS indicators of 14-18 year old children of the male group, the ChRSP of the exhaust gas ranged from 50.0 to 56.4 sm, which averaged 53.2 ± 0.40 sm; LDH ranged from 14.0 to 19.0 sm, an average of 16.5 ± 0.40 sm; THS ranged from 11.4 to 17.0 sm, the average was 13.8 ± 0.11 sm; TFS within 10.8-13.5 sm, an average of 11.8 ± 0.48 sm and VHS ranged from 12.6 to 16.4 sm, which averaged 14.0 ± 0.98 sm.

The results obtained by morphometric characteristics of the head and DFS values in healthy children show that in 6–9 year old women, the group of female children varied the HG ranged from 50.0 to 56.8 sm, on average - 52.5 ± 0.1 sm; LDH from 13.5 to 19.22 sm, on average - 15.9 ± 0.02 sm; THS from 11.8 to 16.8 sm, on average - 13.9 ± 0.25 sm; TFS from 10.1 to 12.5 sm, on average - 10.6 ± 0.22 sm and VHS from 10.8 to 13.9 sm, on average - 12.6 ± 0.23 sm.

HG indices with ChRSP, which in a 6–9 year old group of female children ranged from 48.2 to 54.8 sm, an average of 51.4 ± 0.82 sm; LDH from 12.4 to 18.20 sm, on average - 14.9 ± 0.42 sm; THS from 10.8 to 14.8 sm, on average - 12.5 ± 0.46 sm; TFS from 10.0 to 12.0 sm, on average - 11.0 ± 0.22 sm and VHS from 10.4 to 13.9 sm, on average - 11.8 ± 0.23 sm.

The tendency to increase the head size of the girl's health continued in 10–13 year old girls ($P < 0.05$). The results show that their exhaust gas ranged from 51.0 to 58.0 sm, which averaged 53.4 ± 0.14 sm;

LDH ranged from 14.8 to 18.2 sm, an average of -16.2 ± 0.05 sm;

THS ranged from 12.8 to 15.6 sm, on average - 14.0 ± 0.02 sm, and TFS was in the range of 11.6-13.8 sm, on average - 11.1 ± 0.06 sm and VHS ranged from 11.9 to 14.2 sm, on average - 12.9 ± 0.06 sm.

In girls of these ages, with ChRSP, HG ranged from 49.0 to 56.2 sm, which averaged 52.2 ± 0.24 sm;

LDH ranged from 14.0 to 16.2 sm, an average of -15.0 ± 0.05 sm;

THS ranged from 12.0 to 14.4 sm, an average of 13.2 ± 0.22 sm;

TFS was in the range of 10.0-10.8 sm, on average - 10.4 ± 0.46 sm and VHS ranged from 11.0 to 13.6 sm, on average - 12.2 ± 0.06 sm.

In the health of female children 14-18 years old, the HG varied from 48.8 to 58.8 sm, which averaged 54.0 ± 0.24 sm; LDH ranged from 16.8 to 24.8 sm, an average of 20.0 ± 0.10 sm; THS from 10.4 to 21.8 sm, the average was 16.2 ± 0.20 sm; TFS was in the range of 10.2-16.2 sm, an average of 13.4 ± 0.10 sm and VHS ranged from 16.0 to 20.0 sm, which averaged 18.0 ± 0.10 sm.

In female children aged 14-18 years, with ChRSP, HG ranged from 46.4 to 54.4 sm, which averaged 50.0 ± 0.94 sm; LDH ranged from 14.4 to 22.6 sm, an average of 18.0 ± 0.63 sm; THS ranged from 10.0 to 18.8 sm, averaging 15.2 ± 0.40 sm; TFS was in the range of 9.6-14.2 sm, an average of 11.8 ± 0.40 sm and VHS ranged from 15.4 to 18.2 sm, which averaged 16.0 ± 0.80 sm.

The study of facial parameters in 6-10 year old male children's health showed that the zygomatic diameter (ZD) was in the range from 8.0 sm to 12.1 sm, on average - 9.6 ± 0.24 sm, and l/j diameter varied from 6.8 to 11.4 sm, on average - 8.6 ± 0.28 sm. At this age, male children with ChRSP showed that diabetes ranged from 8.0 sm to 10.1 cm, on average - $8, 8 \pm 0.06$ sm, and l/j, the diameter ranged from 6.6 to 9.0 sm, an average of 7.2 ± 0.07 sm.

The study of facial parameters in 6-10 year old male children's health showed that the zygomatic diameter (ZD) was in the range from 8.0 sm to 12.1 sm, on average - 9.6 ± 0.24 sm, and l/j diameter varied from 6.8 to 11.4 sm, on average - 8.6 ± 0.28 sm. At this age, male children with ChRSP showed that diabetes ranged from 8.0 sm to 10.1 sm, on average - $8, 8 \pm 0.06$ sm, and l/j, the diameter ranged from 6.6 to 9.0 sm, an average of 7.2 ± 0.07 sm.

Face sizes in 14-18 year old boys' health ranged from 9.0 sm to 13.4 sm, which averaged 11.8 ± 0.14 sm, and l/j diameter varied from 9.0 to 12, 22 sm, on average - 9.6 ± 0.10 sm. In the face of 14-18 year old boys with chronic renal failure, diabetes ranged from 8.2 sm to 12.0 sm, which averaged $10.2 \pm 0, 14$ sm, and l/j the diameter ranged from 9.0 to 11.0 sm, on average - 9.0 ± 0.10 sm.

Anthropometric parameters of the face were also studied in healthy female children of 6–9 years old - diabetes ranged from 8.8 sm to 12.0 sm, on average, 10.4 ± 0.16 sm; l/j diameter of the face is from 7.6 to 9.9 sm, on average 8.3 ± 0.12 sm. For children of 6–9-year-old women with ChRSP, it was shown that the size of the face diabetes varied from 8.2 sm to 9.8.0 sm, on average - 8.8 ± 0.04 sm; l/j face diameter from 6.4 to 8.4 sm, on average - 7.2 ± 0.05 sm.

The trend of a gradual increase in face size in practically healthy girls continued in 10-13 year-old girls ($P < 0.05$); Face diabetes ranged from 9.9 to 11.8 sm, an average of 11.0 ± 0.14 sm; l/j diameter is from 7.8 to 9.9 sm, an average of 8.9 ± 0.20 sm. For these age-related girls with ChRSP, it was shown that the size of diabetes was from 8.0 sm to 10.5 sm, on average - 9.0 ± 0.06 sm, and l/j diameters from 6.5 to 8.5 sm, on average 7.3 ± 0.04 sm.

The trend of facial size increase in healthy girls continued in 14-18 year old girls ($P < 0.05$); their facial diabetes is from 11.9 to 13.8 sm, an average of 12.4 ± 0.24 sm; l/j, the diameter is from 8.8 to 10.4 sm, an average of 9.0 ± 0.8 sm. Parameters of facial diabetes in 14-18 year old girls with ChRSP fluctuated from 9.0 to 11.2 sm, an average of $10, 1 \pm 0.26$ sm; l/j diameter from 6.8 to 8.8 sm, an average of 7.7 ± 0.22 sm.

V. Conclusion

1. Body weight in healthy children aged 6-9 years increases faster than body length; in males from 6-9 years, growth increases by 1.57 times, in females 1.64 times; and body weight is 2.71 times in boys, and in women is 2.79 times. The dimensions of the circumference of the chest in a pause of 10-13 years in healthy males increases by 1.44 times, and in females -1.45 times.
2. It was found that comparative indicators of the morphometric parameters of the head of healthy girls and girls with ChRSP of 6–9 years showed that the studied parameters of the head significantly differed from each other. In girls with ChRSP, all parameters were significantly lower than in practically healthy girls.
3. Comparison of the morphometric parameters of boys from 6-9 and 10-13 years old, sick with ChRSP with the parameters of girls of this age, sick with ChRSP, which is the growth rate according to the parameters of HG, LDH, THS, TFS, VHS, according to ZD and l/j the diameter in boys is greater than in girls; l/j, the diameter in male children of patients with ChRSP increases more than in healthy children (1.38 versus 1.29).

4. It was revealed that MHF and PhHF in children with ChRSP are less than in healthy children. The growth rate of the anthropometric parameters of the face in healthy children is almost the same at regular intervals of time, and in children with ChRSP they change spasmodically.
5. It was revealed that the ratio of the upper, middle and lower parts of the face in girls of all groups is closer to the "principle of the golden ratio", compared with boys. In children with ChRSP, especially in boys, the ratio of the parts of the face does not correspond to the Fibonacci number: An analysis of bone age in children with ChRSP showed that their bone age is later than in healthy children; from 6 months (6-9 years) to 2.5-3 years (at 10-13 years).

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